

7.1 Country Brief: A social psychological perspective on trends of extremism in Serbia

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About the Project

D.Rad is a comparative study of radicalisation and polarisation in Europe and beyond. It aims to identify the actors, networks, and broader social contexts driving radicalisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad conceptualises this through the I-GAP spectrum (injustice-grievance-alienation-polarisation) to move towards measurable evaluations of de-radicalisation programmes. We intend to identify the building blocks of radicalisation, including a sense of being victimised, being thwarted or lacking agency in established legal and political structures and coming under the influence of “us vs them” identity formulations.

D.Rad benefits from an exceptional breadth of backgrounds. The project spans national contexts, including the UK, France, Italy, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Finland, Slovenia, Bosnia, Serbia, Kosovo, Israel, Turkey, Georgia, Austria, and several minority nationalisms. It bridges academic disciplines ranging from political science and cultural studies to social psychology and artificial intelligence. Dissemination methods include D.Rad labs, D.Rad hubs, policy papers, academic workshops, visual outputs and digital galleries. As such, D.Rad establishes a rigorous foundation to test practical interventions geared to prevention, inclusion and de-radicalisation.

With the possibility of capturing the trajectories of seventeen nations and several minority nations, the project will provide a unique evidence base for the comparative analysis of law and policy as nation-states adapt to new security challenges. Mapping these varieties and their link to national contexts is crucial in uncovering strengths and weaknesses in existing interventions. Furthermore, D.Rad accounts for the problem that radicalisation processes often occur in circumstances that escape the control and scrutiny of traditional national justice frameworks. The participation of AI professionals in modelling, analysing and devising solutions to online radicalisation is central to the project’s aims.

Executive Summary

This country brief summarises the survey findings for Serbia. It then embeds the survey findings within a national and cultural context for each country. The aim of these summaries is to situate the findings within their respective sociopolitical and sociocultural contexts. The literature review and rationale for the proposed model, analysis of the full dataset, and discussion can be found in the full 7.1 report, which also contains the country briefs.

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1. Results

Serbia had 29.22% of participants reporting not knowing their political attitudes. This variable was subsequently excluded from the model, keeping all participants, and resulting in a final sample of $n = 332$.

Descriptives

Breakdown by age and sex.

Mean age (SD)	Sex					
	Male		Female		Other	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
25.30 (4.34)	165	49.70	166	50.00	1	0.30

Breakdown by religious affiliation.

	n	%
Christian	283	85.24
Agnostic/Atheist	27	8.13
Other	13	3.92
Muslim	9	2.71
Jewish	0	0.00
Buddhist	0	0.00
Bahá'í	0	0.00
Hindu	0	0.00
Sikh	0	0.00

Would you describe yourself as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in this country?

	n	%
Yes	50	21.92
No	255	70.89
Don't know	27	7.19

Breakdown of belonging to a group that is discriminated against.

On what grounds is your group discriminated against?

	n	%
Nationality	18	36.00
Religion	16	32.00
Gender	13	26.00
Language	10	20.00
Sexuality	10	20.00
Colour or race	8	16.00
Ethnic group	5	10.00
Other	5	10.00
Age	4	8.00
Disability	0	0.00

Note: participants were allowed to select multiple groups. As such, proportions will not necessarily add to 100%

Breakdown of different organizations participants reported being members of (active or inactive) or not.

	Active		Inactive		Not a member	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Church or religious organization	120	36.14	107	32.23	105	31.63
Sport or recreational organization	97	29.22	77	23.19	158	47.59
Art, music or educational organization	94	28.31	79	23.80	159	47.89
Labour union	38	11.45	83	25.00	211	63.55
Political party	26	7.83	70	21.08	236	71.08
Environmental organization	56	16.87	70	21.08	206	62.05
Professional association	33	9.94	62	18.67	237	71.39
Humanitarian or charitable organization	102	30.72	61	18.37	169	50.90
Consumer organization	40	12.05	63	18.98	229	68.98
Self-help group or mutual help group	42	12.65	63	18.98	227	68.37
Women's group	45	13.55	61	18.37	226	68.07
Other organization	25	7.53	39	11.75	268	80.72

Breakdown of different political actions participants reported taking in the last 12 months.

Yes		No		Missing value	
n	%	n	%	n	%

Contacted a politician or government official	56	16.87	242	72.89	34	10.24
Worked in a political party or action group	39	11.75	267	80.42	26	7.83
Worked in another ideological organization	29	8.73	273	82.23	30	9.04
Displayed a campaign badge/sticker	39	11.75	267	80.42	26	7.83
Signed a petition	197	59.34	110	33.13	25	7.53
Took part in a lawful public demonstration	78	23.49	232	69.88	22	6.63
Boycotted certain products	123	37.05	185	55.72	24	7.23
Posted or shared anything about politics online	105	31.63	200	60.24	27	8.13

Predictors of realistic threat

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was linked with greater perceptions of threat to one's national ingroup from migrants regarding access to resources, wealth, and power. Perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived than migrants was associated with perceiving more threat. Greater feelings of anomie also predicted perceiving more threat from migrants to Serbia and its resources.

Direct predictors of extremism

Holding stronger beliefs about inherent group hierarchies (social dominance orientation) was associated with more support of extremist attitudes. Perceiving one's social group to be superior (collective narcissism) was linked with increased support of extremist attitudes. In addition, perceiving that one's national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants (group relative deprivation) was also linked with greater support for extremism. In terms of vulnerability, experiencing more social alienation was linked with increased endorsement of extremist attitudes.

Indirect predictors on extremism

The effect of social dominance orientation on support for extremist attitudes was mediated by collective narcissism: a higher social dominance orientation predicted increased collective narcissism, which in turn predicted increased support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect (i.e., the sum of all indirect effects, be these statistically significant or not) of social dominance orientation on extremist attitudes was non-significant, which suggests the combination of all the influences of social dominance orientation through the mediating variables does not predict support for extremist attitudes, even if the effect through collective narcissism when controlling for all other variables, did.

Online group identity also had an indirect effect on extremist attitudes via collective narcissism. A stronger online group identity predicted increased collective narcissism, which then predicted greater support for extremist attitudes. The total indirect effect was not statistically significant, meaning online group identity does not predict extremism when considering all the relationships to the mediating variables.

Figure 15. Respecified model for Serbia

Predictors of attitudes towards Russian culture, Russian and Ukrainian migrants

Perceiving that one’s national ingroup was more economically deprived relative to migrants was associated with more negative attitudes towards Russia. Additionally, holding more trust in the Polish government was also linked with more negative attitudes towards Russia and Russian culture. Increased endorsement of extremism also predicted more negative attitudes towards Russia. In contrast, holding a more populist ideology was linked with improved attitudes towards Russia.

None of the variables of interest (i.e. social dominance orientation, online group identity, collective narcissism, anomie, individual and group relative deprivation, social cohesion, social alienation, populism, political trust, perceptions of migrants as realistic threats, support for extremist attitudes) reliably predicted attitudes towards Russian migrants. In contrast, perceiving that migrants in general were a greater threat towards Serbia and its resources was linked with worsening attitudes towards Ukrainian migrants in the past twelve months.

2. Situating the findings within the Serbian context

The radicalisation patterns in Serbia are deeply rooted in its past, particularly in the turbulent 1990s, which is why it is necessary to glance back at those past events. During this time, the country faced ethnic intolerance, separatist ambitions, political instability, and international isolation, along with violent episodes and participation in ethnic wars. As a result, xenophobic views among the Serbian population were prevalent. The overthrow of Slobodan Milošević’s regime in 2000 marked a significant turning point, leading to comprehensive political,

economic, and cultural transformations. The assassination of Serbian Prime Minister Zoran Djindjić in 2003 hindered the government's ability to sustain its reforms. Furthermore, Kosovo's unilateral declaration of independence in 2008 fuelled ethnic tensions and frustrations in Serbian society. Thus, ethnoreligious polarisations fuelled by legacies of wars, collective grievances, conflicting historical narratives, identity crisis, and lack of opportunities emerge as dominant drivers of radicalisation in Serbia, which is a manifestation of the “socially embedded culture of extremism” (Halilovic Pastuovic et al., 2022, p. 5).

Since 2012, Serbia has experienced a slide into authoritarianism under the rule of the Serbian Progressive Party (SNS), resulting in its lowest democracy score in twenty years and the normalisation of extremist discourses (Tatalović, 2021). Far-right extremism, legitimised during Milošević's rule, shifted focus to internal enemies like minorities, LGBT+, and migrants after being strengthened by the ruling party SNS.

Traditional and conservative attitudes are predominant in villages and smaller towns, while in some larger urban areas, more liberal thoughts oppose conservative and far-right stances. People living in rural areas tend to trust the church more and prefer populist leadership than those living in urban areas (Vucicevic & Jovic, 2020). Regional inequality and urban-rural economic disparities are quite pronounced in Serbia; thus, financial setbacks and poverty in rural areas are related to the growing populism in society (RTS, 2018). Though populism is stronger in peri-urban areas, a rise in populist and far-right attitudes has been noted throughout Serbia recently, especially in the capital city.

In geographical terms, radicalisation trends are more visible going from the country's north towards its central and southern regions. Northern parts of Serbia (Vojvodina region) are populated with different minorities, which could explain higher tolerance towards migrants and less extremist stances. The far-right is concentrated in Belgrade and the central part of the country, while Islamist extremists are located primarily in the Southern region of the country (Sanžak region), in Novi Pazar as a political seat, though they tend to attract Muslims in other parts of the country to spread their influence (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023; Halilovic Pastuovic et al., 2022). The youth, especially in the South and South-West regions, are susceptible to Islamic radicalisation due to religious identity, socioeconomic challenges, and perceived discrimination.

Both right-wing and Islamist extremism can reinforce each other, further exacerbating the situation. As the latest research indicates, far-right extremism in Serbia is on the rise while violent Islamist extremism is in decline, though its non-violent forms are experiencing an increase (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023; RAN, 2022). The particular danger stems from online spaces and social media, where extremist narratives are being proliferated, normalised and mainstreamed, which is especially obvious since the outbreak of the pandemic and war in Ukraine (RAN, 2022). Since 2020 and 2021, Serbia has been experiencing a wave of protests against lockdowns, vaccines, migrants (coming from the Middle East), EuroPride (September 2022), as well as rallies in support of Russia (starting in March 2022), all organised by far-right extremist groups and political parties. Many of the far-right groups have close links with the ruling party and enjoy the support of the Government, which uses them for different purposes (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023). Furthermore, following the onset of the Ukrainian war in

February 2022, a large number of Russian and Ukrainian migrants and refugees came to Serbia. Understanding this complex context is essential for interpreting the D.Rad survey results.

D.Rad survey findings indicate a direct positive correlation between collective narcissism and increased support for extremist attitudes. In the context of Serbian radicalisation, the prevailing narrative suggests that Serbs consider themselves genetically superior, more intelligent, stronger, and better-looking than others, particularly when compared to Muslims (BIRN, 2014). “Serbs are a heavenly people”, as claimed by the Serbian nationalist narrative (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023, p. 10). The notion of Serbian supremacy over others is embraced by certain right-wing groups that are actively present in today's society, especially those whose primary rhetoric revolves around glorifying the conflicts of the 1990s and war criminals. Some of the right-wing extremist groups that advocate white supremacy are Blood and Honour Serbia and the *National Serbian Front* (Buljubašić, 2022).

Higher levels of Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) and a stronger online group identity were found to predict heightened collective narcissism. Consequently, both SDO and online group identity had a small, indirect, positive impact on the support for extremist attitudes through collective narcissism. At the same time, other mediators did not significantly influence the results. Stronger online group identity was found to predict increased social cohesion, but it did not directly impact extremism. Participants who belonged to one or more discriminated groups displayed a stronger online group identity than those who were not part of any discriminated groups. As mentioned earlier, online group identity exhibited only an indirect positive effect on supporting extremist attitudes via collective narcissism. However, surprisingly, this survey did not establish a connection between online group identity and the perception of migrants as a threat to Serbia. The D.Rad survey findings come as a surprise as online radicalisation in Serbia is on the rise as extremists use ethnic identity, hate and conspiracies to proliferate extremist narratives and fake news, particularly regarding the coronavirus pandemic and the war in Ukraine, especially in the existing climate where elites rely upon “manipulation of collective traumas to promote *otherness*” (RAN, 2022, p. 3). Moreover, anti-immigration rhetoric is central to online content shared by far-right (Buljubašić, 2022; RAN, 2022). The sudden increase in these narratives coincides with the pandemic outbreak as people went online more than ever before, and it was the most efficient way to attract vulnerable people to join them.

One such extremist group is *Narodna patrola (People's Patrol)*. The group is very active on social networks, where its members share hateful anti-immigrant content, calling for violence and protests against migrants (Sejdinović, 2021). Extremist propaganda is being legitimised on social media, highlighting the danger of Islamisation of Serbia due to migrant settlements (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2022; Jakovljević, 2021). For example, the Facebook group *STOP Naseljavanju migranata (STOP Migrant Settlement)*, which advocated the expulsion of migrants due to the danger of population and culture change, had 330,000 followers (Rogač, 2021). Current research indicates that ethnic and religious polarisations, as well as political and societal divisions, are being reinforced by hate narratives in online space, which stem from the legacies of past wars. This is particularly evident regarding Muslim migrants as the Balkans and Serbia have been marked as the latest line of defence of Christian frontiers (Buljubašić, 2022; RAN, 2022). As far-right extremists use online groups to share hate

narratives, there is a growing threat of online recruitment for participating in the war in Ukraine on the side of Russia (Buljubašić, 2022; RAN, 2022).

Unlike online group identity, SDO also directly influences extremism. There exists a clear positive correlation between SDO and support for extremist attitudes. Higher SDO levels predict greater endorsement of nationalism, racism, sexism, discrimination, and violence as a means of maintaining the established group hierarchy (Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021). The main narrative of Serbian nationalists revolves around historical rights and the establishment of Greater Serbia. This far-right project is rooted in the belief that parts of Serbian land, along with its people, were taken away during the wars of the 1990s, particularly the Kosovo War in 1999. Consequently, the unification of these lost territories is regarded as the ultimate goal, fuelling extremist ideas and actions (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023; Buljubašić, 2022). This nationalist rhetoric is predominantly utilised by the leading Serbian Progressive Party and the Serbian President Vučić (until recently, he occupied the position of the Party's leader), who exercises considerable control over almost all media in Serbia, constantly shaping public opinion (Ruge, 2023). Despite variations in their discourses, far-right movements and groups find common ground in their focus on the issue of Kosovo, which serves as a unifying force and mobilises the entire far-right spectrum. Kosovo is vital in Serbian national identity, and the prolonged tensions surrounding it have further escalated far-right sentiments. This trend was evident during the 2022 parliamentary elections, where such views gained legitimacy and significant media attention, leading to the normalisation of far-right discourse and rhetoric, especially in the statements of the president himself, who, assuming an authoritarian and dominant political role, strategically employs nationalist discourse to consolidate his political power (Ruge, 2023). The example of Kosovo is frequently used to illustrate potential future scenarios for the rest of Orthodox Serbia, which has already experienced the loss of its cultural cradle (Kosovo and Metohija) to (primarily) Muslims, leading to concerns about the Serbian Orthodox people becoming a minority in the future.

Many populist initiatives, as well as far-right politicians, have been announcing for some time already that Serbia confronts a large number of migrants who will change the population structure of "white" Serbia and Europe (Pejić, 2020). These activities further fuel xenophobic attitudes that have been present since the 1990s. Consequently, there exists a complex interplay of interconnected drivers, with ethnonationalism and religious factors emerging as the most potent predictors of extremism in Serbia. Furthermore, as numerous studies have confirmed, the religious component appears to exert significant influence, surpassing ethnic divisions and extending its impact beyond the boundaries of different ethnic groups (Halilovic Pastuovic et al., 2022; Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021). Apart from the prevalent Serbian Orthodox Church and the Orthodox Christian identity that holds sway over the majority of Serbia, there is also a robust Muslim identity, particularly noticeable in the southern regions, primarily the Sandžak region, where Islamist radicalisation and extremism have been observed. In Serbia, two rival Islamic Communities are operating under the auspices of Belgrade and Sarajevo, respectively, where such division creates a breeding ground for fundamentalist influence from abroad (Halilovic Pastuovic et al., 2022). However, it is the perception of discrimination of the Bosniak community by the central government that ignites the radicalisation flame in the Sandžak region. This conflict dates back to the 1990s and has generated tensions, further reinforced by high youth unemployment and economic

hardships (Cultural Centre DamaD, 2015). In broad terms, extremism in Serbia, whether originating from far-right or Islamist ideologies, possesses a strong religious component that contributes to polarisation.

As revealed by the D.Rad survey results, respondents who do not identify as part of any discriminated groups exhibit slightly higher levels of Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) than those who perceive themselves as discriminated. This aligns with the (far-right) extremist discourse that relies on discriminating against certain groups based on race, ethnicity, religion, or other characteristics. However, it is worth noting that discriminated against groups still demonstrate strong SDO, which could potentially lead to a shift in positions, resulting in the increasing dominance of groups previously discriminated against (Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021). Among the targeted groups, the Roma community has faced significant discrimination from various extremist groups, making their situation a crucial human rights issue in Serbia. In this context, it is essential to draw attention to the problem of Roma radicalisation, which has been identified as a growing trend among Roma Muslims. (Djorić, 2021; Tatalović, 2021).

Perception of social injustice serves as a significant driver of radicalisation and extremism in Serbia. In light of these notions, it is crucial to highlight the findings of the D.Rad survey concerning social alienation, which identified a positive correlation between social alienation and support for extremist attitudes. According to the D.Rad survey, an increased perception of social exclusion directly predicts extremist attitudes. In the region of Sandžak, situated in one of the most economically disadvantaged areas of the country with high rates of youth unemployment, many young people are advocating for some level of regional autonomy or, in more extreme cases, even secession (Cultural Centre DamaD, 2015). The underlying reason for such attitudes lies in the perception of marginalisation and social injustice (Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021), particularly concerning the rights of minorities in Serbia. In this specific case, the region is predominantly inhabited by the Bosniak ethnic group, who primarily identify as Muslims. As revealed in the research of Cultural Centre DamaD on extremism in Novi Pazar, some respondents expressed their views about the government in Belgrade, stating, "...this government in Belgrade is a gang... People here in general, almost everyone, think of Belgrade as an enemy" (Cultural Centre DamaD, 2015, p. 27). This sentiment indicates a strong feeling of rejection towards Belgrade, which holds the political power, leading to increased dissatisfaction and fuelling extremist ideas and sentiments. It can be concluded that their extremist attitudes, fuelled by social alienation, are primarily directed towards the central government. Many research studies indicate that these extremists tend to isolate themselves from other groups, and many of them come from backgrounds with family dysfunction and have a history of exposure to hostile social environments (Cultural Centre DamaD, 2015; Vukčević Marković, Nicović & Živanović, 2021).

In addition to its direct and indirect impact (via collective narcissism) on support for extremist attitudes, higher SDO scores are also associated with negative attitudes towards immigrants. Even after controlling for any effects through collective narcissism, anomie, or perceived individual or group relative deprivation, the survey findings revealed a direct positive correlation between SDO and an increased perception that migrants pose a realistic threat to Serbia and its resources. Increased SDO predicts negative attitudes towards immigrants, as

well as prejudice and resistance to their assimilation within the Serbian cultural context. The dominant Serbian Orthodox identity plays a significant role in Serbian society, and preserving its top position remains a priority (Buljubašić, 2022). From this standpoint, extremist attitudes and anti-immigration sentiments arise. Muslims have long been portrayed as wanting to suppress Christians and seize ancestral lands, fuelling fears that they might eventually become the majority in the country, leaving Serbians as a minority in their homeland (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2022). This far-right discourse aligns with broader far-right rhetoric in the European Union, where migrants are often perceived as threats to ethnic and religious identity. Conservative political discourses also aim to curb immigration. Respondents with higher SDO scores tend to view migrants as threatening the status quo they wish to preserve. There is a fear that once assimilated into the dominant culture, immigrants might exceed its boundaries and bring about change. The dominant narrative concerns the Islamisation of Serbia and complete demographic and cultural change due to migrants settling in Serbian land (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2022; Jakovljević, 2021). During 2020, there were many protests against migrants in cities like Belgrade, Požarevac, Šid, and Subotica organised by different populist initiatives like *Narodne patrole (People's Patrols)* (Rogač, 2021). Serbian citizens perceived migrants as one of the greatest threats to external and internal security (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2022). In 2022, there was a significant increase in the number of migrants coming from Afghanistan, Syria, and Pakistan who used the Balkan route to reach the European Union (FoNet, N1 Beograd, 2022), which revived far-right xenophobic narratives.

When it comes to the Russian and Ukrainian migrants, the perception is quite different. The Serbian Orthodox identity is projected as dominant and superior to immigrants who do not share the same religion. The perceived threat from migrants is related to those coming from the Middle East, while it is not the case with Russian and Ukrainian migrants. This observation further supports the hypothesis of the significant role of religious identity in shaping attitudes towards immigrants. The D.Rad survey results indicate that respondents in Serbia have developed more positive feelings towards Russian migrants over the past 12 months, while their perceptions of Ukrainian migrants have remained relatively unchanged, hovering near a neutral standpoint. This favourable perception towards Russians can be attributed to shared religious identity (Christian Orthodox), historical connections with the Russian people, and a sense of having similar culture and traditional values. Interestingly, none of the variables tested could reliably predict changes in opinions towards Russian migrants over the mentioned period, implying that Russians are not perceived as a threat to Serbian national and religious identity.

On the contrary, increased perceptions of migrants as a realistic threat corresponded with worsened opinions towards Ukrainian migrants over the same 12-month period. The reasons behind this negative perception towards Ukrainians might vary and require further examination. Still, it is evident that this group of migrants is seen as posing a potential threat in some capacity, leading to unfavourable opinions among the respondents. The reason behind such attitudes might be found in pro-Russian media reporting, as well as the influence of far-right narratives regarding the war in Ukraine (Ranković, 2023).

While individual relative deprivation (individual relative deprivation) did not show statistical relevance, group relative deprivation (group relative deprivation) emerged as a highly significant predictor of extremism and anti-immigrant sentiments.

The D.Rad survey findings indicated a direct positive relationship between group relative deprivation and both the perception of migrants as a threat to Serbia and its resources and increased support for extremist attitudes. Notably, the perception of migrants from the Middle East and Russia/Ukraine has undergone a shift. Although Russian and Ukrainian migrants and refugees are generally perceived positively in terms of identity, migrants from Arab nations are not as favourably viewed. However, economic factors play a significant role in influencing sentiments towards these migrant groups. Migrants from the Middle East are often perceived as economically disadvantaged and more deprived than Serbian nationals, while Russian and Ukrainian migrants and refugees are seen as financially better off. Following the onset of the war in Ukraine in February 2022, numerous Ukrainians seeking refuge from the conflict and Russians evading conscription in their home country found solace in Serbia, where they sought opportunities to work and live. Many registered their businesses, while numerous companies that hired individuals from these countries also established branches in Serbia, primarily in Belgrade, enticing people to move to the country (Rakic, 2022). The influx of Russians and Ukrainians was so substantial during the initial months that rental prices skyrocketed. This surge in housing costs posed a significant challenge for Serbian citizens, who could not afford such exorbitant rents, leading to feelings of deprivation within their own country. Numerous students encountered considerable housing difficulties due to their inability to afford apartments in Belgrade. Moreover, many Serbian citizens, including families, were evicted from their rented apartments by landlords who opted to rent to wealthy Russians and Ukrainians, often without regard for the price (Matić, 2022). The dire housing situation that Serbian citizens face due to the arrival of Russian and Ukrainian migrants has heightened feelings of social injustice, marginalisation, and frustration. The inability to secure affordable housing, directly attributed to the presence of these migrants, fuels negative sentiments and exacerbates existing grievances within the Serbian population.

The D.Rad survey also found that older participants perceived the economic situation of nationals compared to migrants worse, indicating a correlation between age and group relative deprivation. Similarly, the survey revealed that increased group relative deprivation, along with increased political trust and support for extremist attitudes, predicted worsened attitudes against Russia. The reasons behind such attitudes towards Russia might be related to the high inflation rate following the war in Ukraine and the influence of opposition forces (mainly centre-left) who advocate for the introduction of sanctions on Russia. The Democratic Party, the Party of Freedom and Justice, and the Green-left coalition are some of the opposition parties calling for imposing sanctions on Russia to align with the EU foreign policy (Pujkilović, 2022). These factors contribute to the complex interplay of perceptions and attitudes observed in Serbian society.

On the other hand, age was positively correlated with greater support for populism, which, in turn, was associated with improved attitudes towards Russia. In that context, it is relevant to mention that in March 2022, the first rally in support of Russia and the Russian invasion of Ukraine was held in Belgrade, gathering several thousand people, and it was initiated by the

populist group *People's Patrol* (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023). Soon after, rallies in support of Russia were held in many other Serbian cities. Online space was flooded with different right-wing profiles and channels that spread propaganda, especially on the Telegram social network, and many far-right extremists from Serbia went to Ukraine to fight on Russia's side (Petrović & Ignjatijević, 2023). Polls from 2022 show that Serbs strongly support Russia and its leader, Putin, and attribute the blame for the war in Ukraine to NATO and the US, seeing Ukraine as a Western puppet (Ruge, 2022). Latest polls also show that most Serbian citizens are against joining the EU for the first time in history (Danas, 2022). The reason behind such attitudes is severe pressure regarding introducing sanctions against Russia and recognising Kosovo as a condition for entering the EU.

The most prominent finding of the D.Rad survey indicates that social domination orientation is one of the strongest predictors of both support for extremist attitudes and increased perception of migrants as a realistic threat. This relationship is both direct and indirect (via collective narcissism). As shown in the discussion above, the far-right in Serbia is on the rise and its extremist narratives are being mainstreamed and normalised thanks to the support of the ruling party, SNS and the Government. Strong national and religious identity shapes the perception of migrants as threats where migrants from the Middle East, who do not share the same values, are perceived as a severe security threat to Serbia and its population structure, which is not the case with Russian and Ukrainian migrants, who are more or less welcomed in Serbia. However, group relative deprivation emerged as a significant predictor of negative attitudes towards migrants and greater support for extremism. The reason behind such attitudes might be the frustration of Serbian citizens with economic setbacks (high inflation and unreasonably high rents) caused by the arrival of Russian and Ukrainian migrants, who are perceived as financially better off.

The radicalisation context in Serbia is inextricably related to political divisions, so the missing political attitudes dimension in the D.Rad survey would have provided essential insights into current radicalisation trends and enabled more profound conclusions regarding the researched topic.

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